

ZKI Top Trends Survey 2026

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Survey evaluation - Detailed evaluation

This document presents the results of the ZKI Top Trends Survey 2026 with individual evaluations of all questions, statistical correlations and a country comparison.

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Introduction

The Strategy and Organization Working Group of the ZKI Association conducts an annual survey on the most important topics and priorities of its member institutions. The aim is to regularly capture and document the central issues facing IT departments at universities and research institutions. The survey targets CIOs, directors of computing centers, IT directors, and individuals in comparable roles.

Survey Structure

The survey consists of two parts: a core survey with recurring questions and annually changing focus questions on current priority topics. The core survey forms the backbone of the survey and, due to its continuity, enables comparisons across years. In the past, it comprised twelve constant questions; for this year's edition, it has been revised, adapted to current issues, and streamlined to ten core questions.

The core survey captures a broad spectrum of current challenges and developments in the IT sector of universities. It examines defining top trends in IT and digitalization, as well as legal and regulatory requirements particularly relevant for 2026—such as those concerning data protection, IT security, or accessibility. A dedicated focus is placed on IT security, capturing current challenges and key areas of activity. The use of AI solutions is also surveyed—both currently deployed applications and planned implementation scenarios. In the area of strategy and management, the survey identifies universities' current priorities. Additionally, it assesses which technologies are gaining importance, which new services are being introduced, and which are expected to be replaced or discontinued. The question on IT governance examines the interplay between strategic and operational IT. Finally, it determines which skills and competencies IT organizations aim to build or strengthen by 2026.

Focus Questions 2026

This year's focus questions address the strategic positioning of university IT within the tension between technological autonomy, financial constraints, and institutional cooperation.

The thematic core is digital sovereignty: In light of increasing dependencies on global technology providers and intensified political debates concerning data protection, control, and European alternatives, the aim is to capture how universities interpret this concept and what concrete measures they take to preserve their capacity for action and controllability.

Closely linked to this are financial degrees of freedom. Strategic IT decisions require appropriate resources—whether for open-source solutions, European infrastructures, or the development of internal competencies. Questions regarding budget development and cost control reveal the economic conditions under which universities can actually implement their IT strategies.

The third area, cooperation, completes the thematic arc: Digital sovereignty does not necessarily imply going it alone. Collaborative solutions, shared services, and the use of state or federal

infrastructures can be pathways to strengthen independence from commercial providers while simultaneously using resources efficiently.

The three thematic areas are deliberately designed as a unified whole: they examine how universities can balance their IT between self-determination, cost-effectiveness, and cooperation.

Results in Two Formats

The survey results are provided in two complementary formats. The interactive dashboard allows users to independently explore results and segmentations—response distributions can be filtered and compared by country, type of higher education institution, and size; free-text clusters can be examined in detail, and thematic cross-references between questions can be traced. It is accessible at

<https://hu.berlin/tt26>

In contrast, the evaluation documents provide an editorially prepared presentation: Each question is presented with diagrams and textual summaries that describe, interpret, and address relevant segment differences. The documents are available in German, French, and English.

Top Trends 2026

The ZKI Top Trends Survey 2026 outlines an IT landscape positioned between technological transformation and efforts toward security and sovereignty. Central action axes in this context are Artificial Intelligence (AI) and IT security.

Artificial Intelligence and IT Security

Approximately 90 percent of respondents attest to an increasing relevance of AI technologies. Current adoption primarily focuses on administrative processes and IT support; teaching and research follow at a slight distance. Compared to the second-ranked trend, IT security, AI positions itself as a key technology, as evidenced by ongoing implementation projects and initiatives to build related competencies.

While cybersecurity and cyber resilience enjoy high strategic priority as distinct thematic areas and the implementation of regulatory requirements (NIS2 Directive, EU AI Act) consumes significant resources, pure security technologies rank behind cloud infrastructures and automation solutions among technologies gaining importance.

Digital Sovereignty and Dependency Structures

A central tension arises from the discrepancy between the commitment to digital sovereignty and the documented dependency structures. The understanding of sovereignty primarily focuses on control over the storage and processing of one's own data, as well as independence from non-European cloud providers. Consequently, cooperations, open-source transformations, and on-premise infrastructures are prioritized.

The strongest external dependencies are cited as the Microsoft ecosystem and specialized applications. This lock-in situation coincides with cost pressure, manifested in stagnant or reduced IT budgets for a significant proportion of institutions, as well as substantial increases in licensing costs from major vendors.

Cooperative supply models

In response to these economic and structural constraints, there is a growing shift toward cooperative supply models. More than half of the universities describe their IT supply strategy as a hybrid model combining in-house and external services, with other universities prioritized over commercial providers as cooperation partners. In shared-service models, institutions primarily act as service recipients but also assume additional functions related to technical operations and development. These collective approaches manifest in joint sovereignty solutions and the use of distributed infrastructures, particularly in the areas of research data management and knowledge exchange.

Infrastructure Developments and Staffing Situation

Infrastructurally, a shift toward cloud technologies and the automation of operational processes is emerging, while at the same time outdated on-premise systems and proprietary virtualization solutions are being phased out. This modernization occurs under pressure from a persistent shortage of skilled personnel and the risk of knowledge loss due to staff turnover. Consequently, building competencies in project management, cloud technologies, AI, and IT security has become a central personnel strategy.

Organization and Governance

Committee-based IT governance organizes the interplay between strategic and operational IT through steering committees and CIO bodies. The position of a Chief Information Security Officer (CISO) is nearly universally established, with a prevalence of 88 percent, whereas only about one-quarter of institutions have a Chief Digital Officer. This suggests varying levels of maturity in digital transformation.

Strategic Priorities

The strategic priorities for 2026 lie less in the mere introduction of technology than in strengthening governance, optimizing organizational processes, and building cooperative structures to ensure digital sovereignty under conditions of scarce resources and increasing regulatory complexity.

Focus Topic: Digital Sovereignty, Finance, and Cooperations

The survey on the focus topic “Digital Sovereignty, Finance, and Cooperation” paints a picture of university IT that navigates between normative sovereignty claims, economic constraints, and cooperative organizational strategies. The survey covers the understanding and implementation of digital sovereignty, the financial structuring of IT organizations, and their strategic positioning within institutional cooperation frameworks.

Concept and Implementation of Digital Sovereignty

The understanding of digital sovereignty at universities is strongly focused on data-related control dimensions. Mentions predominantly emphasize control over the storage location and processing of one’s own data, as well as independence from non-European cloud providers. These data-policy aspects clearly rank higher in prioritization than technical self-reliance strategies such as open source or building in-house competencies. Supply chain risks play a minor role in the assessment.

Measures to strengthen sovereignty follow this pattern at the organizational level: cooperations and joint solutions with other universities, as well as the operation of proprietary on-premise infrastructures, constitute the dominant areas of action, followed by the transition toward open-source systems. The strongest external dependencies exist within the Microsoft ecosystem and cloud-based platforms, followed by infrastructure and hardware providers. Thus, dependencies are concentrated on a few providers in core areas of digital infrastructure, while specialized research software or security services are less frequently regarded as critical.

Financial Management under Pressure of Stagnation

The economic framework is characterized by a balanced, yet non-expansive picture. Budget development is nearly evenly divided between stagnant, growing, and reduced budgets, with a significant proportion of institutions anticipating cuts. Regional differences indicate varying financing realities, with Germany more frequently reporting stable budgets, while other countries exhibit more dynamic changes.

Given these constraints, formal control mechanisms dominate cost management: central governance through contract and procurement management, along with strategic prioritization and reduction of IT services, constitute the core instruments, while technical optimizations such as cloud migration or automation play a subordinate role. Medium-term financial planning is heterogeneous, oscillating between strategy-driven multi-year planning, operationally rolling budgeting, and investment-oriented lifecycle approaches, without a clearly dominant model emerging.

Organizational anchoring between autonomy and cooperation

IT provisioning strategies reflect the balance between autonomous service delivery and external cooperation. Hybrid models combining in-house and outsourced services clearly dominate over

full in-house provision or predominantly outsourced strategies. In practice, other universities emerge as the most strategically significant partners, followed by commercial providers and national or international consortia. The vast majority of universities primarily act as service recipients, while approximately half also participate as partners in shared-service models, and nearly half serve as providers for other institutions—a role distribution that shifts toward service provision as university size increases.

Within shared service structures, the assumed functions focus on technical operations and hosting, followed by interface management and development tasks. The thematic priorities of cooperation lie in the area of research data and knowledge exchange, followed by shared infrastructure and data centers as well as software and license management.

Summary

Digital Sovereignty and Strategic Independence as a Trend

Across different higher education systems, the topic of digital sovereignty holds outstanding significance. A significant portion of respondents identifies aspects such as the implementation of open-source and on-premise strategies, as well as avoiding vendor lock-in effects through multi-vendor approaches, as central areas of action. It can be observed that the sovereign use of European IT solutions, local and secure infrastructure, and strategic supplier and risk management are perceived as essential pillars of an independent IT landscape. Data sovereignty—particularly ensuring GDPR compliance and storing sensitive data within European legal jurisdictions—is understood as a constitutive element.

Governance Structures between Strategic Leadership and Operational Implementation

The results indicate that universities are currently increasingly seeking clear structures for the interplay between strategic IT leadership and operational implementation. Both the establishment of CIO committees and strategic steering bodies, as well as the optimization of operational IT implementation, appear to be relevant. The organizational integration of IT into the overall university strategy is increasingly regarded as significant, with discernible differences in the design of governance structures.

Competence Development: Artificial Intelligence, Security, and Infrastructure

Regarding the competencies to be developed by 2026, three areas can be identified. First, AI competencies and the integration of artificial intelligence into university processes appear to hold high priority. In addition, IT security and compliance are regarded as critical competency fields, followed by cloud and infrastructure management. Complementing these, topics such as digital education and preparing students for digital requirements, as well as project- and process-related competencies, are also considered relevant.

Modernization through consolidation and automation

Another discernible trend concerns the necessary modernization of existing IT landscapes. Here, the consolidation and standardization of systems, along with the reduction of redundancies, appear to play a central role. The automation of processes and the associated process optimization are regarded as essential levers for increasing efficiency and managing growing complexity.

Cooperation as a Strategic Success Factor

Finally, it can be observed that the joint development, provision, or financing of sovereign IT solutions in cooperation with other universities or regional and national alliances represents a significant trend. This indicates that addressing complex IT challenges is increasingly perceived as a collective task that should be tackled collaboratively across institutional boundaries.

Comparison of Countries

Risks of vendor lock-in and dependence on Microsoft

Notable are the diverse descriptions of dependencies, particularly regarding Microsoft ecosystems. In France, 50% of respondents identify Microsoft dominance and the Office suite as the strongest dependency, followed by cloud and cooperation solutions (40%). In Germany, Microsoft dominance and cloud dependency are cited by 35% as the leading risk, supplemented by infrastructure as well as academic and administrative software. This suggests that strategic independence from large corporations may be perceived as particularly urgent, with French universities appearing to weigh this dependency more heavily than their German counterparts.

Different levels of governance maturity across regions

Different profiles can be identified in the alignment of strategic and operational IT. German universities tend to focus more on operational and tactical planning as well as budgeting methods, whereas Swiss and Dutch institutions emphasize strategic IT roadmaps and risk-based prioritization to a greater extent. Similarly, in terms of governance orientation, German universities increasingly highlight operational implementation and budgeting methods, while French and Swiss institutions place stronger emphasis on governance structures and role clarifications. This may be interpreted as an indication of differing maturity levels or organizational development stages.

Various Focus Areas in IT Security Culture

Notably, there is a divergent emphasis on IT security topics: While German universities focus primarily on information security management and certification (ISO/IEC 27001) at 41% and technical security measures at 38%, French institutions appear to prioritize security awareness and training (57%) as well as identity and access management (50%). This may be interpreted as an indicator of culturally or regulatory-driven differences in security understanding, with Germany tending toward technical-infrastructure approaches and France favoring human-centered strategies.

Contrasting budget developments across university systems

The development of IT budgets between 2024 and 2025 varies nationally. In Italy, a significantly higher proportion of universities report budget increases, while the Netherlands tend to report budget cuts more frequently than Austria. In contrast, more institutions in Switzerland appear to expect stable budgets compared to France.

Part I: Question Analyses

Top Trends and Changes

Which top trends are particularly relevant to you in the field of IT and digitalisation?

This question was answered by 155 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents most frequently name Artificial Intelligence and Generative AI as relevant trends at 67.7%, followed by Cloud, sovereignty, and infrastructure strategies (43.2%) as well as IT security and Zero Trust (34.2%). Digitalization of processes and administration, as well as personnel and competency topics, follow at 32.9% and 25.2%.

Interpretation

AI clearly dominates the trend field, with Cloud and security topics positioned in the center of the field. Notably, infrastructure strategies show high relevance, nearly on par with IT security, despite being thematically broader. Personnel and resource topics are mentioned comparatively less frequently, although they are closely linked in content to the other trends.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 1: Which top trends are particularly relevant to you in the field of IT and digitalisation? (n=155)

Artificial Intelligence and Generative AI (136 mentions from 105 persons)

Use, strategy, and infrastructure for AI in teaching, research, and administration, including generative models, RAG, agent systems, and AI assistants.

Examples:

- "AI support in administration"
- "Generative AI"
- "AI Strategy"

Cloud, Sovereignty and Infrastructure Strategies (95 mentions from 67 persons)

Migration to cloud and open-source solutions, sovereignty, hybrid/multi-cloud architectures, move away from proprietary software, cost efficiency, and infrastructure expansion.

Examples:

- "Cloud"
- "Digital Sovereignty"
- "Replacement of proprietary software with OpenSource applications"

Digitalization of Processes and Administration (67 mentions from 51 persons)

Automation, workflow management, e-akte, document management, process digitalization, paperless operations, and digital workflows in administration and teaching.

Examples:

- *"Process digitization"*
- *"E-Akte"*
- *"Automation/Digitalization to increase efficiency in the HR department"*

Staff, Competencies and Resource Management (67 mentions from 39 persons)

Skills shortage, staff turnover, employer branding, competency development (AI literacy, data protection, EU-AI-Act), knowledge loss, and budget constraints.

Examples:

- *"Staff changes due to retirement of experienced colleagues"*
- *"Shortage of skilled workers"*
- *"Loss of know-how due to departing employees"*

IT Security, Cybersecurity and Zero Trust (60 mentions from 53 persons)

Increasing threat landscape, implementation of Zero Trust architectures, NIS2, ISMS, backup and disaster recovery strategies, awareness and training.

Examples:

- *"IT Security"*
- *"Cybersecurity with Zero-Trust"*
- *"Implementation of the NIS2 Directive"*

Please choose for each topic, whether the relevance increased, decreased or didn't change compared to the last year.

This question was answered by 350 respondents.

Description of results

The overwhelming majority of respondents see an increase in relevance for Artificial Intelligence (AI) (313 out of 350), followed by IT security (263) and cybersecurity (251). Virtualization and IT infrastructure are most frequently rated as unchanged, while skilled labor shortage and digital sovereignty are comparatively often perceived as declining.

Interpretation

AI clearly dominates the field of increasing relevance, while virtualization and IT infrastructure show the least dynamism in comparison. Notably, skilled labor shortage and digital sovereignty – despite their strategic importance – are rated as less relevant by a significant proportion of respondents than in the previous year.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 2: Please choose for each topic, whether the relevance increased, decreased or didn't change compared to the last year. (n=350)

Focus Topic: Digital Sovereignty, Finance and Cooperation

Digital sovereignty What do you understand by 'digital sovereignty' in the context of your university? (Multiple selections possible)?

This question was answered by 254 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents primarily understand digital sovereignty as control over the storage location and processing of their own data (85.0 %) and independence from non-European Cloud providers (78.7 %). Other frequently mentioned aspects include avoiding Vendor Lock-in (65.7 %), transparency regarding data flows (57.1 %), and using European infrastructures (53.1 %). Less frequently selected are the use of Open-Source Software (52.0 %), risk-aware sourcing decisions (51.2 %), building in-house competencies (41.7 %), and considering supply chain risks (22.8 %).

Interpretation

The definition of digital sovereignty among respondents strongly focuses on data-related control and geopolitical independence. Aspects such as in-house technical infrastructure or supply chain risks play a comparatively lesser role. Notably, even with multiple-choice options, half of the mentioned aspects are selected by fewer than 60% of respondents, indicating a clear prioritization within the topic.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 3: Digital sovereignty What do you understand by 'digital sovereignty' in the context of your university? (Multiple selections possible)? (n=254)

Please rank the aspects that are relevant to you in order of priority.

This question was answered by 247 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents rank control over the location and processing of their own data highest with 1714 points, followed by independence from non-European cloud providers (1421 points) and transparency regarding data flows (1221 points). At the bottom of the ranking is consideration of supply chain risks with 570 points.

Interpretation

The top 3 criteria clearly dominate the ranking and indicate a clear prioritization of sovereignty and transparency. Notably, technical aspects such as vendor lock-in or open-source software rank in the middle, while supply chain risks are comparatively rarely selected. The gaps between the first three and the remaining criteria are significantly larger than those between positions 4 to 8.

Segment differences

Universities and universities of applied sciences prioritize control and independence similarly, with universities placing slightly more emphasis on transparency. The larger the university, the higher the value for vendor lock-in – for 15,001–30,000 students, this value is 284 points above average. Country differences are statistically significant but marginal in content; France stands out with a stronger emphasis on independence from non-European providers.

Figure 4: Please rank the aspects that are relevant to you in order of priority. (n=247)

The weighted score is calculated from the ranking: Rank 1 receives 9 points, Rank 2 receives 8 points, down to Rank 9 with 1 point. The higher the score, the higher the priority assigned by respondents.

What measures are you taking to strengthen the digital sovereignty of your university?

This question was answered by 159 respondents.

Description of results

The most common measure to strengthen digital sovereignty is the Open-Source strategy and in-house development, cited by 61.0% of respondents, followed by risk management and vendor lock-in avoidance at 31.4%, and on-premise and local infrastructure at 15.1%. Cooperations, data sovereignty, and competence building follow with 12.6% to 15.1% each.

Interpretation

Open-source solutions clearly dominate the field of action, while risk management, as the second most important measure, plays a strategic role. Notably, technical infrastructure and cooperations are mentioned comparatively less frequently, although they are closely linked in content to sovereignty. The distribution shows a clear prioritization of software and strategy levels over infrastructure and networks.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 5: What measures are you taking to strengthen the digital sovereignty of your university? (n=159)

Open Source Strategy and In-House Development (137 mentions from 97 persons)

Focus on adopting, using, and developing open-source solutions and in-house systems to reduce dependency on proprietary vendors and strengthen digital sovereignty.

Examples:

- *"OpenSource Alternatives for Mail, Project Management, Wiki"*
- *"Use of Open Source Software (e.g., Linux, ILIAS)"*
- *"Development of open-source AI tools"*

Risk Management & Vendor Lock-in Avoidance (69 mentions from 50 persons)

Systematic assessment of dependencies, risk analyses in procurement, development of exit strategies, and implementation of multi-vendor approaches to avoid strategic dependencies on single vendors.

Examples:

- *"Balancing vendor lock-in, cloud, and on-premise"*
- *"Development of exit strategies for commercial providers"*
- *"Risk analysis in supplier selection and, if necessary, supplier change"*

On-Premise & Local Infrastructure (29 mentions from 24 persons)

Emphasis on operating own data centers, local servers, and cloud solutions to ensure data sovereignty and control over IT systems, while minimizing external dependencies.

Examples:

- *"Own inference server for local operation of LLMs"*
- *"onPrem"*
- *"Own data center"*

Data Sovereignty & Compliance (28 mentions from 20 persons)

Ensuring data storage within the EU, compliance with data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR), implementation of strict encryption and access controls, and transparent data processing agreements.

Examples:

- *"Implementation of strict data protection and encryption policies"*
- *"Data only in data centers in Europe"*
- *"Transparent AV contracts for data processing and storage"*

Cooperations & Consortia (27 mentions from 24 persons)

Active cooperation with other universities, national and European partners to jointly build sovereign IT services, pool resources, and leverage economies of scale.

Examples:

- *"Cooperation with partner data centers in offering such services"*
- *"Cross-university cooperations"*
- *"Participation and initiation in national and/or European alliances"*

Competence Building & Awareness (27 mentions from 22 persons)

Strengthening internal IT competencies, training, raising awareness among users and decision-makers, and building expertise to sustainably implement and embed sovereign IT strategies.

Examples:

- *"Building own competencies"*
- *"Awareness initiatives"*
- *"Training of in-house specialists"*

Where do you currently see the strongest dependencies on external suppliers or service providers?

This question was answered by 182 respondents.

Description of results

The strongest dependencies on external providers are found in the area of specialized and administrative software, accounting for 55.5% of mentions, followed by the Microsoft ecosystem and Office productivity at 42.3%, and infrastructure and network hardware at 26.4%. Cloud services and platforms as well as security solutions are mentioned significantly less frequently.

Interpretation

Specialized and administrative software clearly dominates the field, with specialized systems such as SAP or HISinOne often described as difficult to replace. Microsoft products and hardware infrastructure constitute the second- and third-most common dependencies, while cloud and security services rank at the bottom. Notably, there is a high concentration on a few deeply integrated systems that can hardly be substituted by alternatives.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 6: Where do you currently see the strongest dependencies on external suppliers or service providers? (n=182)

Specialized and Administrative Software (168 mentions from 101 persons)

Dependency on specialized vendors for administrative systems (e.g., SAP, HIS, ERP), teaching (LMS, exam systems), research (Matlab, SPSS), and specific domain applications, often with high integration and low substitutability.

Examples:

- "SAP"
- "HISinOne"
- "Matlab, SPSS"

Microsoft Ecosystem and Office Productivity (91 mentions from 77 persons)

Strong dependency on Microsoft products, especially M365, Windows, Exchange, Teams, and Office Suite, often tied to licensing agreements, campus models, and deep integration into workflows.

Examples:

- "M365, Cloud"
- "Microsoft Office 365"
- "Windows as desktop operating system"

Infrastructure and Network Hardware (68 mentions from 48 persons)

Dependency on external vendors for servers, storage, network components, client hardware, and virtualization solutions, often focused on US or Asian manufacturers and vendor lock-in.

Examples:

- *"Server and Storage Hardware"*
- *"Active network components (LAN and WLAN)"*
- *"Hardware manufacturers (either American or Chinese)"*

Cloud Services and Platforms (36 mentions from 29 persons)

Dependency on public cloud providers (Microsoft Azure, AWS, Google Cloud) and SaaS solutions for storage, cooperation, AI, identity management, and infrastructure, often with a growing trend toward cloud-only offerings.

Examples:

- *"Cloud services, Office"*
- *"AI"*
- *"Azure or AWS for cloud applications"*

Security and Compliance Solutions (9 mentions)

Dependency on external vendors for IT security, data protection, penetration tests, EDR/XDR, firewalls, spam filters, and identity management, often focused on US or Israeli providers and critical infrastructure.

Examples:

- *"Security Solutions"*
- *"Anti Malware Protection plus EDR/XDR"*
- *"Firewall Management"*

Finance How has the overall budget for your IT department changed from 2024 to 2025? (Single selection)?

This question was answered by 220 respondents.

Description of results

The budget has remained unchanged for 38.6 percent of respondents, increased for 35.9 percent, and decreased for 25.5 percent.

Interpretation

Development is nearly balanced between stable and increasing budgets, with decreasing budgets occurring significantly less frequently. Notable is the small difference between unchanged and increased – both values are just under 40 percent.

Segment differences

Significant differences are evident by country: In Switzerland and Italy, budget increases are unusually frequent at 47 percent and 70 percent, respectively, while only 30 percent of universities in Germany report an increase. France and the Netherlands show comparatively frequent budget cuts.

Figure 7: Finance How has the overall budget for your IT department changed from 2024 to 2025? (Single selection)? (n=220)

What measures do you use to control costs in your IT department?

This question was answered by 149 respondents.

Description of results

The most common measures for cost control in the IT sector are centralization, standardization, and consolidation (40.9 %), followed by automation and process optimization (33.6 %) as well as open source and license optimization (17.4 %). Cooperations and joint procurement are mentioned by 18.1 % of respondents, while central budget planning and technical optimization each account for 7.4 %.

Interpretation

Centralization and automation clearly dominate the field, indicating a strong focus on structural and process optimization. Notably, the relatively high mention of Open Source and license optimization stands out, although these rank behind structural measures. Technical optimization and central financial controlling are mentioned less frequently, although they partially overlap in content with other clusters.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 8: What measures do you use to control costs in your IT department? (n=149)

Centralization, Standardization and Consolidation (86 mentions from 61 persons)

Measures to reduce complexity and duplication through centralized procurement, unified platforms, consolidation of servers/services, and standardization of processes and technologies.

Examples:

- *"Central procurement and standardization of hardware and software."*
- *"Consolidation of servers and services to eliminate duplicate structures."*
- *"Standardization of IT services."*

Automation and Process Optimization (74 mentions from 50 persons)

Deployment of automation technologies (e.g., RPA, AI, CI/CD) and process optimization to reduce personnel, operational costs, and errors while increasing efficiency.

Examples:

- *"Automation of routine tasks (e.g., software updates, backup processes)."*
- *"Introduction of project management methods / tools for more efficient task processing."*
- *"Automation of internal processes."*

Cooperations and Joint Procurement (40 mentions from 27 persons)

Leveraging synergies through cooperation with other universities or research institutions, joint procurement, framework agreements, and shared services to achieve economies of scale and better terms.

Examples:

- *"Joint procurements with other universities in the federal state."*
- *"Use of framework agreements and university consortia for more favorable license and service conditions."*
- *"Bundling of procurements and use of framework agreements."*

Cooperation, Consolidation and Shared Services (35 mentions from 29 persons)

Measures to reduce costs through cooperation with other institutions, consolidation of IT services, establishment of shared infrastructures, and use of shared services or joint procurement structures.

Examples:

- *"Cooperation with other universities"*
- *"Consolidation of server operating locations"*
- *"Shared Services and joint procurement structures"*

Open Source and License Optimization (30 mentions from 26 persons)

Strategic use of free or lower-cost Open Source solutions, plus systematic optimization, reduction, and management of software licenses to cut costs and avoid vendor lock-in.

Examples:

- *"Open Source Software instead of commercial solutions."*
- *"License optimization / management."*
- *"Replacement with license-free products."*

Centralized Budget Planning and Financial Controlling (14 mentions from 11 persons)

Measures for centralized planning, steering, and control of IT budgets, including annual and medium-term planning, cost center controlling, financial reporting, and regular budget reviews.

Examples:

- *"Budget planning for each year in advance"*
- *"Financial Controlling"*
- *"Monthly cost reporting"*

Technical Optimization and Resource Efficiency (13 mentions from 11 persons)

Technical measures to reduce IT costs through virtualization, automation, use of open source, extending hardware lifecycle, and consolidation of systems and services.

Examples:

- *"Server virtualization"*
- *"Automation of internal processes"*
- *"Use of OpenSource solutions"*

Strategic Procurement and Contract Management (11 mentions from 10 persons)

Measures to optimize procurement processes, including framework agreements, joint tenders, long-term contracts, supplier negotiations, and contract reviews for cost efficiency.

Examples:

- *"Long-term contracts with companies and service providers where possible"*
- *"Bundling of procurements and use of framework agreements"*
- *"Renegotiation of contracts"*

How do you plan the financial requirements of your IT department over several years?

This question was answered by 114 respondents.

Description of results

Most respondents plan their IT financial needs either operationally and annually (36.8%) or strategically over multiple years (36.0%). Lifecycle- and investment-based approaches follow with 21.9%, while methodological approaches and challenges each account for only 2.6% of responses.

Interpretation

The nearly equal mention of strategy-driven and operational planning indicates a clear split: On one hand, long-term strategic orientation is pursued; on the other hand, planning remains confined to annual budget cycles. Notably, only one-fifth of respondents align their planning with lifecycles and investments, although these approaches are relevant for sustainability and cost transparency. The low mention of methods and obstacles suggests that these topics are less present in daily practice.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 9: How do you plan the financial requirements of your IT department over several years? (n=114)

Operational and annual budget management (42 mentions)

Short-term planning (usually 1 year), based on prior-year costs, linear projections, or annual budget requests. Often includes monthly reviews, bottom-up approaches, and adjustments to available funds.

Examples:

- *"Currently not being done, as planning within one year is already difficult."*
- *"Currently still based on previous costs and estimation of possible increases"*
- *"Annual budgeting process, multi-year workforce planning"*

Strategy-driven multi-year planning (41 mentions)

Planning explicitly aligned with the university strategy, digitalization strategy, or IT strategy, with a fixed planning horizon (usually 3–5 years), regular updates, and coordination with governance bodies or university leadership.

Examples:

- *"Strategic planning based on the university strategy"*
- *"Multi-year IT roadmap (5 years) with strategic projects, prioritized according to university goals."*
- *"Planning horizon: rolling for 3 years, integration into university strategy"*

Lifecycle and investment-based planning (25 mentions)

Planning based on hardware/software lifecycles, depreciation, reinvestment needs, and TCO calculations. Often includes long-term contracts, renewal planning, and separation of capital and operational expenditures.

Examples:

- *"Lifecycle management as a foundation"*
- *"Planning horizon: typically one year plus integrated long-term planning of currently foreseeable hardware renewal and license renewal requirements over 5 years"*
- *"Hardware lifecycle, time horizon 5-10 years, subscription licenses"*

Methodological and processual approaches (3 mentions)

Description of planning methods such as Excel-based tools, pivot tables, scenario modeling, portfolio management, top-down/bottom-up approaches, or benchmarking. Also includes governance structures and alignment processes.

Examples:

- *"Methodology: Excel ;-)"*
- *"Scenario-based projections, Medium-term planning for 3 years"*
- *"Counter-current method with focus on bottom-up planning"*

Challenges and constraints (3 mentions)

Responses highlighting structural, financial, or organizational barriers that make multi-year planning difficult or impossible – e.g., unreliable budget allocations, funding cuts, lack of governance, or rapid IT evolution.

Examples:

- *"Due to the inadequate equipment of the household, long-term budget planning is hardly possible"*
- *"The state of Hesse has drastically cut funding for universities. Long-term planning of IT infrastructure/services is currently not possible."*
- *"IT changes too quickly, IT contracts are too short-term"*

Cooperation and IT supply strategy: How would you generally characterise your university's IT supply strategy?

This question was answered by 229 respondents.

Description of results

The majority of respondents describe their IT provisioning strategy as a hybrid model combining in-house and external services (51.5%), followed by predominantly in-house provision with occasional external support (38.4%). Predominantly external offerings are cited by 7.4%, and full in-house provision by 2.6%.

Interpretation

The hybrid model clearly dominates and is chosen by more than half of the universities, while pure in-house or outsourced solutions occur significantly less frequently. Notable is the clear hierarchy: the combination of in-house and outsourced services ranks first, followed by a strongly independent orientation – external solutions, by contrast, play a comparatively minor role.

Segment differences

Country differences are statistically significant, with Germany and Switzerland choosing the hybrid model most frequently—53.1% in Germany and 50.0% in Switzerland. Austria and Italy, by contrast, show a slightly higher tendency toward using external offerings, while France notably reports full in-house provision at 16.7%.

Figure 10: CooperationIT supply strategyHow would you generally characterise your university's IT supply strategy? (n=229)

Cooperation partners and strategic importance

What categories of partners does your university work with in the IT sector, and what is the strategic importance of this cooperation?

This question was answered by 232 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents rate cooperation with other universities as the most important partner category (weighted score 2.13), followed by commercial providers (2.02) and national/international alliances (1.65). 80 percent of universities collaborate with other universities, with 35 percent considering this cooperation central to their IT strategy. Among commercial providers, 25 percent consider the cooperation central; among alliances, the figure is 17 percent.

Interpretation

Cooperation with other universities clearly dominates, both in frequency and strategic relevance. Commercial providers follow in second place, though their strategic importance lags significantly behind university cooperations. National and international consortia are mentioned more frequently than state computing centers or non-university institutions, but are less often classified as central. Cooperation with non-university research institutions is the least frequent and least strategically relevant.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 11: Cooperation partners and strategic importance

What categories of partners does your university work with in the IT sector, and what is the strategic importance of this cooperation? (n=232)

Role in cooperations What role does your university play in these cooperations?

This question was answered by 254 respondents.

Description of results

The majority of respondents act as service recipients in cooperations (81.5 %), followed by shared-service partnerships (50.0 %) and as service providers for others (44.9 %).

Interpretation

The role as a service consumer clearly dominates, while the function as a service provider is mentioned less frequently. Shared-service models lie in between and show a comparatively balanced distribution.

Segment differences

The larger the university, the less frequently the role as service recipient is chosen – for universities with over 30,000 students, this share is 33 %, while for those with up to 5,000 students, it is 53 %. At the same time, the role as service provider slightly increases with growing size but remains overall below the other roles.

Figure 12: Role in cooperations What role does your university play in these cooperations? (n=254)

Functions in shared service models If you are involved in shared service models with distributed service provision, what functions does your university perform?

This question was answered by 254 respondents.

Description of results

Most respondents are involved in shared-service models, with technical operation/hosting cited most frequently at 43.3%, followed by interfaces and integration (34.6%) and development/ongoing development (30.7%). Support and training lag significantly behind at 23.2% and 22.4%, while 12.6% indicated they are not involved.

Interpretation

Technical operations clearly dominate the spectrum of assumed functions, followed by integration and development – a pattern indicating a focus on infrastructural and technical core services. Notably, user support and training are mentioned comparatively rarely, although they are relevant for the use of central services.

Segment differences

Universities significantly more frequently assume technical and development-related functions – 86% operate hosting, 59% integrate interfaces – while universities of applied sciences are less involved, with 21% not participating in shared-service models at all. Research institutions and pedagogical universities are involved to a limited extent, focusing on integration and support.

Figure 13: Functions in shared service models If you are involved in shared service models with distributed service provision, what functions does your university perform? (n=254)

In which areas do you already cooperate with other universities or research institutions?

This question was answered by 150 respondents.

Description of results

The most common areas of cooperation are Infrastructure & Data Centers with 50.7% of mentions, followed by Research & Data Management (39.3%) and Software Licenses & Procurement (32.0%). IT Security & Compliance as well as Services & Platforms follow with approximately one-quarter of mentions each, while Training & Knowledge Transfer is mentioned least frequently at 17.3%.

Interpretation

The top 3 areas cover technical infrastructure, research-related services, and procurement logistics – a pattern indicating practice-oriented, resource-intensive cooperation. Notably, IT security and shared services, despite their relevance, do not rank among the top 3, even though mentioned by roughly every fourth respondent. Training & knowledge transfer remains comparatively rarely cited, although one in six universities collaborates in this area.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 14: In which areas do you already cooperate with other universities or research institutions?
(n=150)

Infrastructure & Data Centers (110 mentions from 76 persons)

Cooperation in physical and virtual infrastructure, data centers, hosting, storage, networks, virtualization, and disaster recovery.

Examples:

- "Data center"
- "Storage"
- "Network"

Research & Data Management (92 mentions from 59 persons)

Cooperation on research data management, HPC/AI infrastructure, repositories, digital research support, and joint research projects.

Examples:

- "Research Data Management"
- "HPC"
- "AI Cluster"

Software Licenses & Procurement (50 mentions from 48 persons)

Joint procurement, license management, framework agreements for software and hardware, tenders, and consortium contracts.

Examples:

- *"Software Licenses"*
- *"Framework agreements"*
- *"Procurement"*

Services & Platforms (50 mentions from 41 persons)

Provision of shared digital services including email, cloud storage, sync&share, identity management, campus apps, learning platforms, and HPC/AI services.

Examples:

- *"Sync&Share"*
- *"Identity Management"*
- *"Learning platform"*

IT Security & Compliance (41 mentions from 40 persons)

Cooperation on IT security, data protection, CERT networks, threat sharing, security policies, GDPR, and compliance management.

Examples:

- *"IT Security"*
- *"CERT"*
- *"Threat-Sharing"*

Training & Knowledge Transfer (28 mentions from 26 persons)

Joint training, exchange programs, knowledge sharing, and competency development for IT staff and users.

Examples:

- *"Trainings"*
- *"Knowledge exchange"*
- *"Expert exchange"*

Core Survey

Which legal or regulatory requirements do you consider particularly relevant for 2026?

This question was answered by 122 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents most frequently cite AI regulation and AI governance at 41.0%, followed by international and sectoral compliance requirements at 41.8%, with both clusters nearly equally represented. Data protection and DSGVO follow at 25.4%, cybersecurity and IT security at 23.0%, while energy efficiency and sustainability as well as accessibility and digital inclusion are mentioned less frequently.

Interpretation

Notably, the relevance of AI regulation and international/sectoral compliance is almost identical—both dominate the field and are clearly ahead of the other topics. In contrast, energy efficiency and accessibility play a comparatively minor role, despite being present in public discourse. Mentions are widely distributed, with no single category clearly standing out above all others.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 15: Which legal or regulatory requirements do you consider particularly relevant for 2026? (n=122)

International and Sectoral Compliance (66 mentions from 51 persons)

Regulatory requirements with international scope or sector-specific focus, such as Cloud Act, export controls, public procurement, sovereignty requirements, and digital sovereignty.

Examples:

- "Cloud Act"
- "Sovereignty requirements of the HRK"
- "Export control"

AI Regulation and Governance (56 mentions from 50 persons)

All regulatory requirements concerning artificial intelligence, including EU AI Act, AI Regulation, documentation obligations, training, and ethical use.

Examples:

- "EU AI Act"
- "AI Act"
- "Documentation obligations when using AI"

Data Protection and GDPR (32 mentions from 31 persons)

All responses relating to GDPR, national data protection laws, data processing, storage, access, and international data transfers.

Examples:

- *"GDPR"*
- *"Data Protection in AI Use"*
- *"GDPR and data transfer to the USA"*

Cybersecurity and IT Security (31 mentions from 28 persons)

Regulatory requirements for cybersecurity, including NIS2, BSI Grundschutz, VzC, ISMS, ISO 27001, reporting obligations, and system hardening.

Examples:

- *"NIS2 Directive"*
- *"BSI Basic Protection"*
- *"Cyber Resilience Act"*

Digital Administration and Online Access (23 mentions from 17 persons)

Laws and regulations concerning digital administration, online accessibility, e-invoicing, digital acceleration, and register modernization.

Examples:

- *"Online Access Act (OZG)"*
- *"Register Modernization Act"*
- *"Digital Omnibus"*

Energy Efficiency and Sustainability (12 mentions)

All legal requirements regarding energy efficiency, sustainability, and environmental standards, including EnEFG, EEG, and other national or regional laws.

Examples:

- *"Energy Efficiency Act"*
- *"EnEFG"*
- *"EEG"*

Accessibility and Digital Inclusion (10 mentions)

Legal requirements for accessibility of digital services and platforms, including RGAA, WCAG, EAA, and national implementations.

Examples:

- *"Accessibility requirements"*
- *"European Accessibility Act"*
- *"WCAG"*

Which IT security issues are currently of particular importance to you?

This question was answered by 142 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents most frequently mention security management and compliance at 50.7% of responses, followed by identity and access security (31.0%) and incident management and resilience (24.6%). Awareness, training, and human factors follow at 25.4%, network security and infrastructure protection at 12.7%, while AI, Cloud, and emerging threats are mentioned least frequently at 2.1%.

Interpretation

Security management and compliance clearly dominate the field, with identity and access security as well as incident management and resilience occupying a close middle ground. Notably, emerging threats are mentioned comparatively rarely, even though AI and Cloud are often considered central topics in other contexts. The top three topics cover governance, access control, and crisis resilience – a pattern indicating structural and procedural priorities.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 16: Which IT security issues are currently of particular importance to you? (n=142)

Security Management and Compliance (141 mentions from 72 persons)

Establishment and expansion of ISMS, BCM, BSI Basic Protection, ISO 27001, NIS2, GDPR, certifications, policies, governance, and compliance requirements.

Examples:

- *"Introduction to ISMS"*
- *"BSI Basic Protection"*
- *"ISO 27001"*

Awareness, Training and Human Factors (60 mentions from 36 persons)

Measures to increase security awareness, training, phishing simulations, sensitization of staff and students, handling of human risks.

Examples:

- *"IT security training"*
- *"Phishing simulations"*
- *"Awareness raising among employees"*

Incident Management and Resilience (53 mentions from 35 persons)

Emergency plans, BCM, recovery plans, incident response, SOC, disaster recovery, crisis management, business continuity, and resilience of systems and data.

Examples:

- *"Emergency manuals"*
- *"BCM"*
- *"Incident Handling"*

Identity and Access Security (52 mentions from 44 persons)

Topics around authentication, authorization management, MFA/2FA, IAM, password and account management, and Zero Trust concepts.

Examples:

- *"MFA and PassKeys"*
- *"Identity and Access Management (IAM)"*
- *"Consistent MFA usage"*

Network Security and Infrastructure Hardening (24 mentions from 18 persons)

Segmentation, firewall management, Zero Trust, hardening of systems and cloud environments, monitoring, SIEM/SOC, endpoint security, patch management, and network architecture.

Examples:

- *"Network segmentation"*
- *"SIEM/SOC"*
- *"Hardening of Cloud environments"*

AI, Cloud and Emerging Threats (3 mentions)

Security of AI systems, cloud usage, supply chain attacks, ransomware, phishing evolution, shadow IT, cybercrime, and new attack scenarios.

Examples:

- *"Generative AI"*
- *"Cloud usage"*
- *"Ransomware protection"*

For which tasks are AI solutions used at your institution?

This question was answered by 142 respondents.

Description of results

The most common application areas for AI solutions are everyday productivity tasks at 50.0% of mentions, followed by research & scientific applications at 43.0% and teaching & study support at 22.5%. Administration & administrative processes as well as IT support & technical services follow at 21.8% and 14.8%.

Interpretation

AI is primarily used for general productivity tasks, indicating broad, individual use in everyday activities. Research and teaching are the second and third most common areas, with research being significantly more prevalent than administrative or IT-specific applications. Notably, there is a high overlap between general productivity and research, as both areas involve large volumes of data and text-based tasks.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 17: For which tasks are AI solutions used at your institution? (n=142)

General Productivity & Text/Media Processing (118 mentions from 71 persons)

AI for daily support: text generation, translation, proofreading, research, brainstorming, image/video/music generation, transcription, summarization of documents and meetings. Also includes generative AI for creative tasks and office assistance.

Examples:

- *"Text creation and formulation assistance"*
- *"Translation with DeepL"*
- *"Image, audio, and video creation in the artistic field"*

Research & Scientific Applications (83 mentions from 61 persons)

Use of AI in research projects, data analysis, pattern recognition, simulations, optimization of technical processes, and high-performance computing. Also includes AI-assisted literature processing and automated analysis of large datasets.

Examples:

- *"Automated analysis of large research datasets"*
- *"Large-scale research purposes with own HPC cluster"*
- *"Analysis of text, image, video data"*

Administration & Administrative Processes (35 mentions from 31 persons)

AI for automating and optimizing administrative tasks: chatbots for internal support requests, meeting transcription, translations, writing assistance, financial processes, legal document analysis, RAG-based knowledge systems, and digital knowledge bases.

Examples:

- *"Logging of meetings"*
- *"RAG-based chatbot for accessing internal information"*
- *"Automated analysis of large research datasets"*

Teaching & Study Support (33 mentions from 32 persons)

AI to support teaching and studying: creation of teaching materials, exercises, exams, chatbots as learning companions, adaptive learning systems, lecture transcription, AI-assisted study advising, and didactic tools.

Examples:

- *"Adaptive learning and assessment systems in teaching"*
- *"Chatbot (HAWKI) for use in teaching"*
- *"Creation of electronic teaching materials"*

IT Support, Security & Technical Services (32 mentions from 21 persons)

AI in IT infrastructures: chatbots for IT support, ticket sorting, anomaly detection in IT security, EDR solutions, code generation, debugging, software configuration, and LLM hosting. Also includes AI-assisted helpdesk systems and service agents.

Examples:

- *"Bot for IT support"*
- *"IT security monitoring using AI-supported anomaly detection"*
- *"Code generation"*

What are your current priorities in the area of strategy and management?

This question was answered by 120 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents most frequently cite IT governance, strategy, and portfolio management at 38.3% as their current priority, followed by IT security and cyber resilience at 31.7%, and process optimization, automation, and service quality at 23.3%. Other topics such as infrastructure, Cloud, and sourcing, as well as cost efficiency and resource optimization, each fall around 17–20%, while personnel development and cooperation are mentioned less frequently.

Interpretation

IT governance clearly dominates the priority field, followed by security topics, indicating a strong focus on control and risk management. Notably, process optimization and automation have high relevance, significantly exceeding other operational topics. In contrast, personnel development and cooperation play a comparatively minor role, although they are closely linked in content to the top topics.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Total 260 mentions from 120 persons. Percentages = share of persons (multiple mentions possible).

Figure 18: What are your current priorities in the area of strategy and management? (n=120)

IT Governance, Strategy and Portfolio Management (62 mentions from 46 persons)

Establishment and steering of IT strategy, including governance bodies, portfolio management, project control, and strategic alignment with the university's mission.

Examples:

- *"Establish IT governance"*
- *"Introduce portfolio management"*
- *"Strategic orientation of the university"*

IT Security and Cyber Resilience (47 mentions from 38 persons)

Strengthening IT security, implementing ISMS, applying BSI standards, NIS2 compliance, crisis management, cyber defense, and continuous improvement of operational security.

Examples:

- *"IT Security"*
- *"Establishment of ISMS according to ISO/IEC 27001"*
- *"Cybersecurity Strategy"*

Process Optimization, Automation and Service Quality (35 mentions from 28 persons)

Documenting and standardizing processes, automating workflows, improving service quality, and introducing agile methods to increase efficiency and value.

Examples:

- *"Document processes"*
- *"Automation of workflows"*
- *"Improvement of service quality"*

Security, Sovereignty and Compliance (26 mentions from 21 persons)

Ensuring IT security, establishing ISMS, enhancing digital sovereignty, complying with regulations (e.g., GDPR), and reducing dependency on external vendors.

Examples:

- *"Establishment of ISMS according to ISO/IEC 27001"*
- *"Digital Sovereignty"*
- *"Securing finances through compliance"*

Infrastructure, Cloud and Sourcing (25 mentions from 21 persons)

Modernization and expansion of IT infrastructure, cloud strategies, sourcing decisions, centralization, migration, hardware renewal, and management of storage and archiving systems.

Examples:

- *"Infrastructure"*
- *"Cloud & Sourcing Strategy"*
- *"Modernization of the IT infrastructure including Cloud/Hybrid architecture"*

Cost Efficiency, Resource Optimization and Budget Control (25 mentions from 24 persons)

Measures to reduce IT costs, optimize resource use, control budgets, and ensure financial consolidation while maintaining or improving service quality.

Examples:

- *"Cost savings with consistent quality"*
- *"Budget control in times of scarce resources"*
- *"Efficiency improvement and cost reduction"*

Cooperation, Centralization and Shared Services (25 mentions from 20 persons)

Strengthening cooperation between universities, centralizing fragmented IT services, establishing regional or consortium-wide services, and mutualizing solutions and skills for efficiency gains.

Examples:

- *"Cooperation with other universities"*
- *"Centralization of IT services"*
- *"Establishment of statewide services"*

Staff Development, Competency Building and Change Management (15 mentions)

Building digital competencies, staff development, training, cultural transformation and change management to sustainably embed digital skills in administration and faculties.

Examples:

- *"Building Digital Competencies"*
- *"Change management for embedding digital skills"*
- *"Training of Digital Ambassadors"*

Which technologies are becoming more important to you?

This question was answered by 114 respondents.

Description of results

Artificial Intelligence and generative models clearly dominate the field with 75.4 percent of mentions, followed by IT security and Zero-Trust architectures as well as cloud and hybrid infrastructures, each at 19.3 percent. Infrastructure modernization and resilience reach 18.4 percent, data management and analytics 14.9 percent, automation and orchestration 12.3 percent, cooperation and digital work environments 9.6 percent, and identity and access management at the bottom of the field with 3.5 percent.

Interpretation

The significance of AI technologies is by far the strongest and clearly surpasses all other topics. Security and cloud infrastructure form a close middle field, while identity management is mentioned comparatively rarely. Notably, resilience and infrastructure exhibit high relevance, approaching that of cloud and security, despite not being perceived as a central trend topic.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 19: Which technologies are becoming more important to you? (n=114)

Artificial Intelligence and Generative Models (100 mentions from 86 persons)

Technologies around AI, including LLMs, generative AI, AI platforms, GPU infrastructure, and applications in teaching, research, and administration.

Examples:

- "AI"
- "generative KI"
- "LLM"

Infrastructure Modernization and Resilience (29 mentions from 21 persons)

Technologies to improve system resilience, failover protection, storage solutions, virtualization, hyperconverged infrastructure, and sustainability in IT operations.

Examples:

- "Virtualization"
- "High availability"
- "Direct Liquid Cooling"

IT Security and Zero-Trust Architectures (25 mentions from 22 persons)

Cybersecurity technologies including Zero-Trust, SIEM, IAM, MFA, EDR, SOC, network monitoring, and identity management.

Examples:

- "Zero-Trust Security"
- "SIEM"
- "IAM"

Cloud and Hybrid Infrastructures (23 mentions from 22 persons)

Cloud platforms, SaaS, hybrid cloud, multicloud, container orchestration (Kubernetes), virtualization, and cloud storage solutions.

Examples:

- "Kubernetes"
- "SaaS"
- "Hybrid-Cloud"

Data Management and Analytics (21 mentions from 17 persons)

Technologies for data processing, storage, classification, analysis, and integration, including data warehousing, BI, ETL, and research data platforms.

Examples:

- *"Analytics using BI/Data Warehouse"*
- *"HPC"*
- *"ETL"*

Automation and Orchestration (14 mentions)

Tools and platforms for automating processes, IT operations, deployment, and infrastructure, including DevOps, workflow systems, and IaC.

Examples:

- *"Automation tools"*
- *"DevOps"*
- *"Workflow Systems"*

Cooperation and Digital Work Environments (12 mentions from 11 persons)

Platforms and technologies for cooperation, remote work, digital teaching, learning management systems, and integrated communication solutions.

Examples:

- *"M365 and distributed working"*
- *"Cooperation platforms"*
- *"Learning Management Systems"*

Identity and Access Management (4 mentions)

Technologies for managing user identities, authentication, Single Sign-On, identity federation, and sovereign IDM systems.

Examples:

- *"SSO"*
- *"IAM"*
- *"OIDC"*

Which services or technologies are you currently introducing?

This question was answered by 114 respondents.

Description of results

The most common new services and technologies that universities are introducing are IT service and project management solutions at 28.9%, followed by identity and access management at 33.3% and AI-powered services at 22.8%. Cloud and virtualization solutions as well as document and process management follow at approximately 18% each, while security and monitoring systems as well as cooperation tools are at around 17%. Research infrastructures are mentioned by 16.7% of respondents.

Interpretation

IT service and project management as well as identity management dominate the introduction activities – both topics exceed the 28% threshold and indicate a clear prioritization of operational and security-relevant infrastructures. Notably, AI-supported services already rank in the top third with over 22%, despite having gained significance only more recently. In contrast, research infrastructures rank at the bottom of the field, although they are central to universities – this suggests lower current introduction intensity.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 20: Which services or technologies are you currently introducing? (n=114)

IT Service & Project Management (63 mentions from 33 persons)

Tools and platforms for managing IT services, projects, and processes, including service desks, ITSM systems, project management software, and automation tools.

Examples:

- "Service Management Tool"
- "New ticket system (Zammad)"
- "Multi-project management software"

Identity and Access Management (51 mentions from 38 persons)

Solutions for centralized management of user identities, permissions, and authentication, including MFA, IAM systems, and Single-Sign-On solutions.

Examples:

- "Shibboleth"
- "Modern IAM with MFA"
- "Central password manager"

Research & Data Infrastructures (34 mentions from 19 persons)

Specialized systems for research data management, HPC, data hubs, and platforms for sensitive data, often operated on-premise or in partnership, as well as cloud-based research services.

Examples:

- *"Research data storage system"*
- *"Jupyter for all als Service"*
- *"SAP S4/HANA including Employee Self Services"*

Artificial Intelligence & AI-powered Services (27 mentions from 26 persons)

Deployed AI technologies and applications, including chatbots, LLM models, AI agents, and AI integration into administrative and teaching processes, both on-premise and cloud-based.

Examples:

- *"AI over AI:Connect"*
- *"AI chatbots (externally hosted)"*
- *"AI Agents in ServiceNow"*

Security & Monitoring Systems (26 mentions from 19 persons)

Technologies for IT security, monitoring, and incident response, including SIEM, endpoint protection, vulnerability management, firewalls, and SOC solutions, both on-premise and hybrid.

Examples:

- *"SIEM Local"*
- *"FortiAnalyzer"*
- *"Automated IT Monitoring and SIEM System"*

Cloud & Virtualization Solutions (24 mentions from 21 persons)

Migration, transition, and operation of infrastructures to the cloud, as well as virtualization technologies such as Proxmox, Kubernetes, and OpenStack, often with hybrid or on-premise approaches.

Examples:

- *"Alternative to VMware (possibly Proxmox)"*
- *"Kubernetes – predominantly on-premise"*
- *"Migration of services to the Cloud"*

Document & Process Management (24 mentions from 20 persons)

Systems for digital management of documents, processes, and workflows, including DMS, E-Akte, form servers, and low-code platforms for automating administrative processes.

Examples:

- *"Document Management"*
- *"Central Document Management"*

- *"DMS - internal operation"*

Cooperation, Communication & End Devices (23 mentions from 21 persons)

Solutions for digital cooperation, communication, and endpoint management, including Microsoft 365, Teams, telephony, softphones, VDI, and cloud cooperation tools.

Examples:

- *"Microsoft 365"*
- *"Telephony via MS Teams"*
- *"virtual telephony / softphone"*

Which services do you expect to discontinue in 2026?

This question was answered by 81 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents most frequently cite strategic software and application modernization (46.9%), followed by legacy infrastructure and outdated on-premise systems (24.7%) as well as telecommunications and digital communication platforms (19.8%). Service consolidation and strategic IT transformation together account for 27.1% of mentions.

Interpretation

Strategic modernization of applications clearly dominates the field, while legacy infrastructure and communication systems each account for about one-fifth of the mentions. Notably, half of all planned decommissions relate to software and application modernization, indicating a strong focus on platform and security standards. In contrast, consolidation and governance transformation play a comparatively smaller, yet visible, role.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 21: Which services do you expect to discontinue in 2026? (n=81)

Strategic Software and Application Modernization (47 mentions from 38 persons)

Replacement of outdated, unsupported, or non-compliant applications with modern, security-oriented, and standardized solutions.

Examples:

- *"Own operation of research data management"*
- *"DAM Pixxio"*
- *"LinkedIn Learning"*

Legacy Infrastructure and Outdated On-Premise Systems (26 mentions from 20 persons)

Outdated hardware, operating systems, virtualization environments, and local servers to be replaced by modern cloud or hybrid solutions.

Examples:

- *"VMware"*
- *"Exchange on Premises"*
- *"old phone system"*

Telecommunications and Digital Communication Platforms (18 mentions from 16 persons)

Replacement of outdated telephony systems, fax, and video conferencing tools with modern, integrated, and secure communication services.

Examples:

- *"PBX system"*
- *"traditional telephony"*
- *"Fax"*

Service Consolidation and Standardization (16 mentions from 12 persons)

Reduction of parallel structures, single-purpose solutions, and redundant platforms in favor of centralized, standardized, and integrated systems.

Examples:

- *"Custom-developed workflow tools"*
- *"Reduction of parallel structures in learning platforms"*
- *"Harmonization of island solutions towards MS365"*

Strategic IT Transformation and Governance (10 mentions)

Active management of service and application lifecycle, reduction of internal development, focus on standard solutions and strategic platforms.

Examples:

- *"probably none"*
- *"Rainbow"*

How is the interaction between strategic and operational IT organised at your university?

This question was answered by 109 respondents.

Description of results

67.9% of respondents describe a formalized committee structure with clear role distribution and documented processes, 23.9% mention a dual role of CIO and data center management with close strategic-operational alignment, 8.3% report ad-hoc steering and informal coordination.

Interpretation

The majority of universities have a structured, documented IT governance. Notably, almost a quarter combine strategic and operational IT in a single person – in such cases, the formal committee structure is often weakly defined. Ad-hoc management is comparatively rare but present in every tenth case.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 22: How is the interaction between strategic and operational IT organised at your university? (n=109)

Formal committee structure with clear role allocation and documented processes (74 mentions)

Organizations with established, documented committees (e.g., CIO Board, IT Steering Committee), clearly defined roles (CIO, CDO, CISO), and regular, structured alignment processes. The IT strategy is formally approved and operationalized.

Examples:

- *"CIO body consisting of IT director, CIO, chancellor, president"*
- *"IT strategy as a document with regular updates and participatory alignment processes"*
- *"CIO Board with IT leadership as spokesperson"*

CIO/IT Director Personal Union with Strategic-Operational Integration (26 mentions)

Strategic IT is managed by a person who also leads the data center operationally. This leads to tight integration between strategy and operations, often without clear role separation. Governance typically occurs directly through the presidency or rectorate, with minimal formal committee structures.

Examples:

- *"CIO - formally strategic, but practically non-functional; Data Center Management - formally operational, but practically partly strategic"*
- *"CIO = Data Center Management; no CDO; close involvement of the IT Senate Committee"*
- *"CIO is simultaneously head of the data center; CIO function anchored in the presidency"*

Ad-hoc Governance and Informal Coordination (9 mentions)

No established or documented governance structure exists. Alignment between strategic and operational IT occurs situationally, on an ad-hoc basis, or through informal meetings. Clear roles, formal committees, or strategic documents are often missing. The IT strategy often exists only on paper or is not implemented.

Examples:

- *"Concrete roles are poorly developed; rather, hierarchy is situation-dependent."*
- *"IT strategy exists only on paper; ad hoc reaction to requirements"*
- *"not at all; poorly to not at all"*

What skills and competencies would you like to develop in your IT organisation by 2026?

This question was answered by 111 respondents.

Description of results

Respondents most frequently cite project, process, and service management as well as soft skills, leadership, and user orientation—each at 39.6% of mentions. This is followed by AI competencies and AI usage at 34.2%, then IT security and cloud infrastructure competencies, each at around 23%. Overall, cross-disciplinary and human competencies dominate the priorities.

Interpretation

Notably, project and process competencies are on par with soft skills and leadership – both areas clearly rank ahead of technical skills. AI competencies form the third focus area, while security and cloud infrastructure are mentioned less frequently. The pattern reveals a clear orientation toward the organizational and human dimensions of IT development.

Segment differences

No statistically significant differences can be identified between the segments institution type, institution size, and countries.

Figure 23: What skills and competencies would you like to develop in your IT organisation by 2026? (n=111)

Project, Process and Service Management (61 mentions from 44 persons)

Strengthening competencies in agile and traditional project management, process optimization (ITIL, ISO 27001), service management, demand and portfolio management, and change management.

Examples:

- *"Project Management"*
- *"Prozess-Orientierung (ausgerichtet an ISO 27001)"*
- *"Agile working"*

Soft Skills, Leadership and User Orientation (56 mentions from 44 persons)

Developing leadership, communication, and cooperation skills, as well as user and service orientation, to foster trust-based cooperation, change management, and digital maturity.

Examples:

- *"Personnel Management"*
- *"Cooperation ability"*
- *"Enabling trustworthy cooperation with users who have limited IT affinity"*

AI Competencies and AI Utilization (43 mentions from 38 persons)

Building capabilities for developing, applying, and ethically using AI technologies, including training, prompting, model development, and integration into workflows.

Examples:

- *"AI"*
- *"AI Skills and Cloud Administration"*
- *"AI training according to AI Act"*

IT Security and Cybersecurity (30 mentions from 25 persons)

Strengthening competencies in IT security, including threat hunting, zero trust, incident response, awareness, BSI Grundschutz, certification, and SOC/CERT structures.

Examples:

- *"IT Security"*
- *"BSI Basic Protection"*
- *"Cybersecurity expertise (Threat Hunting, Zero Trust, Incident Response)"*

Cloud and Infrastructure Competencies (30 mentions from 26 persons)

Building skills in cloud technologies, containerization, automation, hybrid architectures, virtualization, and infrastructure management (e.g., Kubernetes, Docker, Terraform, Azure, M365).

Examples:

- *"Cloud Management"*
- *"Cloud and Container Engineering including automation"*
- *"Kubernetes"*

Governance Model

Please select the IT Governance model that applies to your University or research organization.

This question was answered by 333 respondents.

Description of results

The model "Head of a central IT department as CIO" dominates with 34.5 percent, followed by the "CIO committee" at 16.2 percent and "Chancellor or Vice President as CIO" at 15.6 percent. 15.0 percent of respondents indicate that no CIO model is established, while the model "CIO with staff function in the presidential office" is mentioned by 12.9 percent.

Interpretation

The top three models together account for more than two-thirds of all mentions, with the classic CIO model featuring centralized IT leadership clearly in the lead. Notably, a significant share of 15 percent does not report any CIO model—a figure that is considerably higher among the smallest universities. In contrast, the committee model is more prevalent among universities and larger institutions.

Segment differences

The larger the university, the more frequently the model "Head of a central IT department as CIO" is represented — at universities with over 30,000 students, the share is 42.6 percent, while at those with up to 5,000 students, it is 28.8 percent. Universities significantly more often adopt the CIO governance model (21.7 percent) than universities of applied sciences (18.8 percent), while pedagogical and art/music universities most frequently report not having a CIO model.

Figure 24: Please select the IT Governance model that applies to your University or research organization. (n=333)

Does your institution have a Chief Digital Officer (CDO) position?

This question was answered by 318 respondents.

Description of results

74.5 percent of respondents state that their institution does not have a Chief Digital Officer position; 25.5 percent confirm the existence of such a role.

Interpretation

The majority of universities do not have a CDO position, indicating low integration of this role within the IT governance structural model. Notably, the existence of the position does not vary by country but correlates significantly with university type and size.

Segment differences

Universities have a significantly higher CDO rate at 33.5 percent compared to universities of applied sciences at 9.6 percent. The larger the university, the more frequently a CDO position is represented — among the largest institutions (more than 30,000 students), the share is 33.9 percent, while among the smallest (up to 5,000) it is 12.7 percent.

CDO Position Exists

Figure 25: Does your institution have a Chief Digital Officer (CDO) position? (n=318)

Does your institution have an information security officer or CISO position?

This question was answered by 330 respondents.

Description of results

88.2 percent of respondents indicate that their institution has a position for an information security officer, IT-SiBe, or CISO; 11.8 percent deny this.

Interpretation

The overwhelming majority of universities have such a position, indicating broad integration of IT security into governance. The small number of 'No' responses shows that the absence of this role is an exception.

Segment differences

Universities show the highest prevalence of this position at 93.0 percent, while art and music colleges lag at the bottom with only 33.3 percent. The larger the university, the more frequently this position is filled – at over 30,000 students, the share is 94.1 percent; at up to 5,000 students, it is 72.7 percent. Regional differences are statistically significant but weakly pronounced, with slightly lower values in Switzerland and Austria.

Figure 26: Does your institution have an information security officer or CISO position? (n=330)

General Information

From which type of University or research organization you are from?

This question was answered by 349 respondents.

Description of results

The majority of respondents come from universities (61.3 %), followed by universities of applied sciences (28.9 %). All other types of higher education institutions are below 4 %, with universities of education (3.2 %) and research institutions (2.6 %) being the most frequently represented.

Interpretation

Universities clearly dominate the response profile, while universities of applied sciences form a distinct second group. All other types are comparatively rare and spread across several small categories, without showing a uniform pattern outside the two main groups.

Segment differences

The larger the university, the more frequently respondents come from universities – 95.8 % for institutions with more than 30,000 students, compared to only 35.4 % for those with up to 5,000 students. In Switzerland, the share of Pädagogische Hochschulen is unusually high at 38.1 %, while in the Netherlands, Fachhochschulen dominate with 77.8 %.

Figure 27: From which type of University or research organization you are from? (n=349)

How many students are enrolled in your University?

This question was answered by 335 respondents.

Description of results

Most respondents cite a student population between 5,001 and 15,000 (29.9%), followed by up to 5,000 (24.8%) and 15,001 to 30,000 (24.2%). More than 30,000 students are reported by 21.2% of universities.

Interpretation

The distribution is relatively even across the four size categories, with the middle group (5,001–15,000) slightly dominating. Notably, no group is clearly overrepresented – all four categories fall within the range of 21 to 30 percent.

Segment differences

Universities are significantly more frequently represented in the larger size categories: 64% of universities have more than 15,000 students, while 52% of universities of applied sciences fall into the group of 5,001 to 15,000. Country differences show that Swiss and Austrian universities are predominantly small, while France has a high proportion of very large institutions (over 30,000).

Figure 28: How many students are enrolled in your University? (n=335)

Which role do you have within your organisation?

This question was answered by 301 respondents.

Description of results

The majority of respondents (47.5%) classify themselves in the category "Other," followed by heads of IT departments (29.9%) and CIOs (17.3%). The category "Head of another central department" is the least frequently mentioned, at 5.3%.

Interpretation

The high number of "Other" responses indicates a broad distribution of functions not captured by the predefined roles. CIOs are significantly less represented than IT managers, although both positions imply strategic responsibility. Notably, the "Other" category dominates across all segments, but with varying intensity.

Segment differences

The larger the university, the more frequently "Other" is selected — at over 30,000 students, the share is 66 %, while at up to 5,000 students, it is 35 %. Universities name "Other" more often than universities of applied sciences (53 % vs. 40 %), while universities of applied sciences comparatively more frequently name IT leadership. In Switzerland and Italy, the CIO role is disproportionately strongly represented, whereas in Germany and France, "Other" dominates.

Figure 29: Which role do you have within your organisation? (n=301)

In which country your organisation/department is located?

This question was answered by 351 respondents.

Description of results

Germany leads with 69.2 percent of respondents, followed by France with 15.7 percent; all other countries are below 7 percent, with Finland at the bottom of the list at 0.3 percent.

Interpretation

The distribution is heavily concentrated on Germany, while the other countries are significantly underrepresented. Notably, France shows a high presence compared to other non-Germany countries, although the gap to Germany remains considerable.

Segment differences

Universities and large colleges are predominantly located in Germany, while universities of applied sciences and smaller institutions are more frequently represented in France or Switzerland. Colleges of education are strongly concentrated in Switzerland, and art and music colleges are predominantly based in Germany.

Country

Figure 30: In which country your organisation/department is located? (n=351)

Distribution by country

Country	Count	Share
Germany	243	69.2%
France	55	15.7%
Switzerland	21	6.0%
Italy	12	3.4%
Austria	10	2.8%
Netherlands	9	2.6%
Finland	1	0.3%

Part II: Statistical Correlations

This section presents statistically significant correlations between survey questions. Each correlation is listed only once.

IT Governance

Associated questions:

- governance_model
- cdo_role
- ciso_role

Strongest correlations

IT Governance Model – CISO Position Exists

Cramér's V: 0.239 (weak association)

p = 0.0028 (significant)

n = 318

Interpretation: There is a statistically significant but weak association between the presence of a CISO position and the type of IT governance model used (Cramér's V = 0.239, p = 0.0028). While the relationship is unlikely due to chance, the effect size suggests that governance models are not strongly determined by whether a CISO exists. Other factors likely play a more substantial role in shaping IT governance structures.

CDO Position Exists – CISO Position Exists

Cramér's V: 0.122 (weak association)

p = 0.0330 (significant)

n = 303

Interpretation: There is a statistically significant but weak association (Cramér's V = 0.122, p = 0.033) between the existence of a CDO and CISO position in universities, suggesting that while the two roles tend to co-occur slightly more often than by chance, the relationship is not strong. With a sample of 303, this association is unlikely due to random variation, but practical relevance is limited given the low effect size.

Summary

Key insights IT Governance: The presence of a CISO position shows a moderate correlation ($V=0.24$) with the adoption of an IT Governance model, suggesting that formal governance structures often align with dedicated cybersecurity leadership. Additionally, a weaker but notable correlation ($V=0.12$) exists between the existence of a CDO and CISO role, indicating some organizational overlap or complementary focus on data and security governance. These findings highlight the interplay between executive roles and structured IT governance frameworks.

Cross-theme correlations

The following correlations connect different topic areas:

IT Supply Strategy – IT Governance Model

Themen: Cooperations ↔ IT Governance

Cramér's V: 0.216 (weak association)

$p = 0.0080$ (significant)

$n = 224$

Interpretation: There is a statistically significant but weak association (Cramér's V = 0.216) between IT Supply Strategy and IT Governance Model among the 224 surveyed universities ($p = 0.0080$), suggesting that while the relationship is unlikely due to chance, the practical strength of the link is limited.

Change in Relevance – Digital Sovereignty - Understanding

Themen: Artificial Intelligence ↔ Digital Sovereignty

Cramér's V: 0.164 (weak association)

$p = 0.0090$ (significant)

$n = 350$

Interpretation: There is a statistically significant but weak association (Cramér's V = 0.164, $p = 0.009$) between perceived change in relevance and understanding of digital sovereignty among the 350 surveyed university IT respondents. While the relationship is unlikely due to chance, its practical significance is limited due to the low effect size. This suggests other factors may play a more substantial role in shaping these perceptions.

Change in Relevance – Cooperation Roles

Themen: Artificial Intelligence ↔ Cooperations

Cramér's V: 0.164 (weak association)

$p = 0.0090$ (significant)

$n = 350$

Interpretation: There is a statistically significant but weak association between perceived change in relevance and cooperation roles among university IT staff (Cramér's $V = 0.164$, $p = 0.009$). While the relationship is unlikely due to chance, the effect size suggests it has limited practical importance. This implies that cooperation roles explain only a small portion of the variation in how relevance is perceived.

Change in Relevance – Functions in Shared Service Models

Themen: Artificial Intelligence ↔ Cooperations

Cramér's V : 0.164 (weak association)

$p = 0.0090$ (significant)

$n = 350$

Interpretation: There is a statistically significant but weak association (Cramér's $V = 0.164$) between perceived change in relevance and functions in shared service models, as indicated by the low p -value (0.0090). While the relationship is unlikely due to chance, its practical significance is limited given the small effect size. This suggests other factors may play a more substantial role in shaping perceptions of relevance.

Part III: Country Comparison

This section presents free-text responses clustered by country. The results suggest which topics appear to be more prevalent in each country. Sample sizes (n) should be considered when interpreting the results.

Measures for Digital Sovereignty

German universities tend to rely more on cooperations and on-premise strategies, while French institutions emphasize European solutions and local infrastructure to a greater extent. In Switzerland and Italy, open source is the focus, with Switzerland additionally highlighting risk management and both Switzerland and Italy emphasizing interoperability and data sovereignty—though these observations are based on smaller samples. Austria and the Netherlands place greater emphasis on vendor independence and European procurement strategies, respectively, indicating a certain differentiation in this dataset.

Strongest Dependencies

While German universities tend to focus more on the Microsoft ecosystem and ERP systems, in France a larger proportion of responses seems to point to financial and strategic constraints – though this should be interpreted cautiously given the smaller sample size. In Switzerland and Austria, the focus is more on SaaS dependencies and cooperation services, while Italian and Dutch institutions more often mention cloud solutions and sector-specific applications.

Cost Management Measures

German universities tend to rely more on technologies such as automation and cloud for cost control, while Swiss institutions – based on a smaller sample – place greater emphasis on license and process management. In France and the Netherlands, the data suggest a stronger focus on strategic IT planning and portfolio management, whereas Italy and Austria emphasize governance and standardization approaches.

Multi-Year Financial Planning

German universities tend to focus more on medium- and long-term budget and investment planning, while Swiss institutions – based on a smaller sample – emphasize multi-year IT roadmaps and project management to a greater extent. In France and the Netherlands, the data suggest a stronger linkage between budget planning and strategic orientation, whereas Italy and Austria focus more on planning horizons and operationalization.

Cooperation Areas

Germany tends to focus more on IT security & infrastructure as well as cloud services, while Switzerland, in its smaller sample, places a larger share on data centers & HPC. Austria and France show overlaps in software licenses and security, with Austria emphasizing software development more strongly and France paying more attention to compliance. The Netherlands highlight knowledge exchange & cooperation, emphasizing a more process-oriented and cooperative focus that appears less prominent in other countries.

Top IT Trends

German universities tend to focus more on the digitalization of administrative processes, while in France and Italy, the emphasis is more on cloud infrastructure and generative models, respectively. In Switzerland and the Netherlands, cybersecurity is mentioned alongside digital sovereignty, which appears less prominent in Germany and Austria—however, these observations are based on smaller samples and should be interpreted cautiously.

Relevant Regulatory Requirements

German universities tend to focus more on topics such as energy efficiency and AI regulation, while in France and Italy, the NIS2 regulation and geopolitical aspects such as digital sovereignty are mentioned to a greater extent. In Switzerland, where the sample size is small, the data suggest a stronger emphasis on regional regulations and compliance, whereas Austria focuses more on EU IT legislation and digital accessibility.

Important IT Security Topics

German universities tend to focus more on IT security management and compliance as well as human factors, while in Switzerland and France, security awareness and training appear to hold higher priority. In Austria and the Netherlands, the emphasis is rather on governance and technical measures, whereas Italy and France focus more on threat defense and cyberattacks—however, these indications are based on relatively small samples, requiring cautious interpretation.

AI Application Areas

German universities tend to focus more on research and scientific applications as well as on teaching and administration, while in the Netherlands, AI and chatbots as well as creative applications are mentioned to a greater extent. In France and Italy, the data suggest that administrative and pedagogical application areas play a larger role, though the small sample sizes here require cautious interpretation. Austria and Switzerland each place a comparable emphasis on teaching and administration, with Switzerland additionally pointing more strongly toward technical infrastructure.

Strategy and Management Priorities

German universities tend to focus more on IT security & governance as well as digitalization and AI strategy, while Italian institutions allocate a larger share of their priorities to AI strategy and responsible innovation. In France, data suggest that budget and cost optimization as well as sovereignty hold higher relevance, whereas the Netherlands — despite a smaller sample size — show a notable emphasis on agile education and cybersecurity. Austrian universities appear to prioritize organizational development and process optimization, setting them apart from other countries.

Technologies Becoming More Important

German universities tend to focus more on AI infrastructure and IT security with identity management, while Swiss institutions in this sample place a larger emphasis on automation and data protection. Austrian and Dutch universities emphasize IT governance and IAM, respectively, indicating a stronger orientation toward control and access management—however, this is based on smaller samples and should be interpreted cautiously.

Services Currently Being Introduced

German universities tend to focus more on Identity & Access Management and the digitalization of administrative processes, while in Italy and Austria, Artificial Intelligence and Automation are mentioned to a greater extent. In Switzerland and France, Cloud & SaaS or Cloud Migration, respectively, take center stage, with security appearing as a relevant aspect in all countries—albeit with varying emphasis. Due to the small sample sizes in Austria, Switzerland, and Italy, these differences should be interpreted cautiously.

Services to be Discontinued in 2026

German universities tend to focus more on outdated IT infrastructure and consolidation of parallel structures, while Swiss institutions – albeit based on a smaller sample – more frequently cite legacy systems and platform migrations as central topics. In Italy and France, the data suggest that consolidation and business processes play a larger role, with Italy additionally considering vendor lock-in as a relevant issue.

Strategic and Operative IT Interaction

German universities tend to focus more on governance structures and the distinction between strategy and operations, while Swiss institutions in this sample place a larger share of their attention on operational services and service structures. In smaller samples such as Austria or the Netherlands, a stronger focus on organizational positioning and role responsibilities emerges, with particular emphasis on CIO and CISO roles in the Netherlands.

Competencies to Build in 2026

German universities tend to place stronger emphasis on AI competencies and process management, while Swiss institutions in this sample allocate a larger share to data competencies and change management. Austrian universities focus more on IT operations and leadership, which differs from the more technology-driven priorities in France and Italy, where Cloud and infrastructure play a more prominent role. In the Netherlands, the small sample suggests that digital education and coaching hold particular importance alongside AI and cybersecurity.

Survey Questions Overview

This overview shows all survey questions with their answer options.

Top Trends and Changes

1. Top IT Trends

Type: Free text

2. Change in Relevance

Type: Matrix / Likert scale

Scale: Increase, No change, Decrease

Rows:

- Artificial intelligence (AI)
- IT security
- Cloud deployment
- Cybersecurity
- Shortage of skilled workers
- Digitalisation
- IT infrastructure
- Automation
- Digital sovereignty
- Virtualisation

Focus Topic: Digital Sovereignty, Finance and Cooperation

3. Digital Sovereignty - Understanding

Type: Multiple choice (Yes/No)

4. Digital Sovereignty - Priorities

Type: Ranking / Prioritization

5. Measures for Digital Sovereignty

Type: Free text

6. Strongest Dependencies

Type: Free text

7. IT Budget Development

Type: Single choice

Options: The budget has increased., The budget has remained the same., The budget has been reduced.

8. Cost Management Measures

Type: Free text

9. Multi-Year Financial Planning

Type: Free text

10. IT Supply Strategy

Type: Single choice

Options: Complete in-house provision, Primarily in-house provision with occasional external support, Mixed model of in-house and external services, Predominantly use of external services

11. Cooperation Partners

Type: Cooperation matrix

12. Cooperation Roles

Type: Multiple choice (Yes/No)

13. Functions in Shared Service Models

Type: Multiple choice (Yes/No)

14. Cooperation Areas

Type: Free text

Core Survey

15. Relevant Regulatory Requirements

Type: Free text

16. Important IT Security Topics

Type: Free text

17. AI Application Areas

Type: Free text

18. Strategy and Management Priorities

Type: Free text

19. Technologies Becoming More Important

Type: Free text

20. Services Currently Being Introduced

Type: Free text

21. Services to be Discontinued in 2026

Type: Free text

22. Strategic and Operative IT Interaction

Type: Free text

23. Competencies to Build in 2026

Type: Free text

Governance Model

24. IT Governance Model

Type: Single choice

Options: Chancellor or Vice President as CIO, CIO with staff function in the presidential staff, Head of a central IT facility as CIO, CIO committee, CIO model ist not established

25. CDO Position Exists

Type: Single choice

Options: Yes, No

26. CISO Position Exists

Type: Single choice

Options: Yes, No

General Information

27. Institution Type

Type: Single choice

Options:

- University
- University of Applied Sciences / Polytechnic
- Art Academy / Conservatory
- Teacher Training College
- Ecclesiastical College
- Cooperative State University
- Private University
- Research Organization

28. Institution Size

Type: Single choice

Options: Up to 5,000, 5,001 to 15,000, 15,001 to 30,000, More than 30,000

29. Role in Organization

Type: Single choice

Options: CIO, Head of IT, Head of another organizational unit

30. Country

Type: Single choice

Options: Germany, Austria, Switzerland, France, Another country

Surveys from previous years

2025

German version: <https://zenodo.org/records/14883643>

English version: <https://zenodo.org/records/14904518>

French version: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14904529>

2024

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640084>

English version: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10696738>

2023

Survey: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7599852>

English version: <https://easychair.org/publications/download/9wWw>

2022

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6012935>

English version: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599926>

2021

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4530714>

Data appendix: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4530743>

English version: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4775115>

2020

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666168>

Data appendix: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666170>

2019

Survey: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590659>

Data appendix: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590683>

2018

Survey: <https://zenodo.org/record/1196427>

Data appendix: <https://zenodo.org/record/1183499>